

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets

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Abstract : Several 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets have been prepared by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide with aryl isothiocyanates. The structure of these new *N*-lactosylated-2,4-isodithiobiurets have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, NMR, and Mass spectral analysis. Antimicrobial activities of these compounds were evaluated.

Keywords : Lactosyl isothiocarbamide, aryl isothiocyanates, isodithiobiurets.

Introduction

N-Lactosides are those compounds in which lactosyl group or its derivatives are attached to the nitrogen of nitrogen containing compounds. This class of compounds has several applications in industries, medicinal chemistry and in many other ways^{1,2}. This type of compounds show antidiabetic and antituberculosis³ significance.

Here we report the synthesis of several *N*-lactosylated-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-f**) prepared by the reaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (**2**) with aryl isothiocyanates (**3a-f**). The required 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (**2**) was obtained by the reaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-thiocarbamide (**1**) with benzyl chloride followed by basification with ammonium hydroxide. Required aryl isothiocyanates were prepared by already known method⁴.

Results and discussion

Several 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-f**) (Scheme 1) were prepared by the reaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (**2**) with aryl isothiocyanates (**3a-f**) in benzene for 3 h. After complete reaction the solvent was distilled off to obtain a sticky residue. This residue was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford the pale yellow products (**4a-f**). The

products were found to be non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline lead acetate. IR spectrum of the product shows characteristic absorption of lactose unit in the range of 900–910, 1000–1100 and 1200–1300 cm^{-1} ^{5,6}. Mass spectra showed the characteristics of lactose unit⁷. All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Experimental

Specific rotations were measured on Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter at 28 °C in CHCl_3 . IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI FTIR spectrophotometer (4000–450 cm^{-1}). ¹H NMR were recorded in CDCl_3 on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer operating at 300 MHz. The Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol-SX-102 (FAB) instrument.

*Preparation of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide :*

A mixture of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-thiocarbamide (**1**) (0.005 *M*, 5.5 g), benzyl chloride (0.005 *M*, 0.64 g) and ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 90 min. The resulting acidic solution when made basic with dil. NH_4OH yielded a solid, which was crystallized with petroleum ether (60–80 °C).

*Synthesis of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**4a-f**) :*

A benzene solution of phenyl isothiocyanate (**3a**) (0.005

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *m*-tolyl, (c) *o*-tolyl, (d) *p*-tolyl, (e) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (f) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (g) *o*-Cl-phenyl

Scheme 1

M, 0.54 g) was added to benzene solution of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (0.005 M, 5.0 g in 40 ml of benzene). After refluxing the reaction mixture for 3 h, a clear solution was obtained. This was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a granular solid. This was crystallized from acetone-ether, m.p. 138–140 °C.

On extending the reaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide with other aryl isothiocyanates several *N*-lactosylated-2,4-isodithiobiurets (4a-f) have been isolated (Table 1). IR⁸, NMR⁹ and Mass¹⁰ spectra of the products were observed. Optical rotation¹¹ of the products were also recorded.

4a : m.p. 140 °C; yield 83%; [α]_D²⁵ + 94° (*c*, 0.140 in CHCl₃); IR(KBr) : 3417 (NH), 1729 (C=O), 1451.2 (C-N), 1270 (C-O), 854.4 (lactosyl C-H deformation), 709.9 cm⁻¹ (C-H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm) : δ 6.18–3.70 (18H, m, 2-NH, 16 lactosyl protons), 8.05–7.18 (45H, m, 7COC₆H₅, 2C₆H₅); Mass (*m/z*) : 1353 (M⁺ + 1), 1053 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 67.34; H, 4.61; N, 3.08; S, 4.52. Calcd. for C₇₆H₆₃O₁₇N₃S₂ : C, 67.40; H, 4.65; N, 3.10; S, 4.73%).

4b : m.p. 132 °C; yield 80%; [α]_D²⁵ + 138° (*c*, 0.140 in CHCl₃); IR(KBr) : 3463 (NH), 1729.4 (C=O),

Table 1. 1-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (4a-f) (Scheme 1)

Reactants : (I) 1-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (2), (II) phenyl isothiocyanates (3a-f)

Product	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Requires)		[α] _D ²⁵ (<i>c</i> , CHCl ₃)
			N	S	
4a	140	83	3.08 (3.10)	4.52 (4.73)	+94° (<i>c</i> , 0.140)
4b	132	80	3.03 (3.07)	4.57 (4.68)	+138° (<i>c</i> , 0.140)
4c	136	79	3.03 (3.07)	4.36 (4.68)	+120° (<i>c</i> , 0.140)
4d	120	85	3.01 (3.07)	4.41 (4.68)	+108° (<i>c</i> , 0.140)
4e	140	78	2.99 (3.02)	4.28 (4.61)	+95° (<i>c</i> , 0.140)
4f	144	75	2.99 (3.02)	4.36 (4.61)	+100° (<i>c</i> , 0.140)

C and H analysis were found satisfactory in all cases.

1451.7 (C-N), 1270.7 (C-O), 854.4 (lactosyl C-H deformation), 709.9 cm^{-1} (C-H aromatic); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (ppm) : δ 6.18–3.80 (18H, m, 2-NH, 16 lactosyl protons), 7.98–7.17 (44H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_5 , C_6H_4), 2.29 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$); Mass (m/z) : 1367 (M^+), 1368 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 1053 (HBL^+), 579 (TBG^+), 391 ($\text{TBG}^+ - \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$), 335 ($\text{TBG} - \text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$), 105 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}^+$) (Found : C, 67.51; H, 4.68; N, 3.03; S, 4.57. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{77}\text{H}_{65}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$: C, 67.59; H, 4.75; N, 3.07; S, 4.68%).

It has been observed that some of these compounds showed nearly the same activity as that of standard amikacin and fluconazole (Table 2). Similarly also it has been observed that these compounds exhibited interesting microbial activities. **4a**, **4b**, **4d** and **4f** exhibited most significant activity against *Salmonella typhi* and *E. coli* while **4e** inhibited *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*. All other compounds exhibited low to moderate activity.

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of compounds (4a-f)

Compd.	Antibacterial ^a				Antifungal ^b	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>C. guilliermondii</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
4a	18	20	20	24	18	17
4b	18	18	17	23	23	22
4c	15	19	18	20	17	16
4d	20	19	17	24	23	22
4e	15	23	23	19	22	23
4f	22	19	17	22	18	19
Amikacin	18	21	23	24	-	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	24	25

^aIncluding the well diameter of 8 mm. ^bZone of inhibition in mm (15 or less) less resistance, (16–20 mm) moderate and (more than 20 mm) sensitive.

4e : m.p. 140 °C; yield 78%; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 95^\circ$ (c, 0.140 in CHCl_3); IR (KBr) : 3420 (NH), 1729.1 (C=O), 1451.9 (C-N), 1270.6 (C-O), 854.4 (lactosyl C-H deformation), 709 cm^{-1} (C-H aromatic); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (ppm) : δ 6.11–3.79 (18H, m, 2-NH, 16 lactosyl protons), 7.98–7.18 (44H, m, $7\text{COC}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_5 , C_6H_4); Mass (m/z) : 1388 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 1053 (HBL^+), 579 (TBG^+), 391 ($\text{TBG}^+ - \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$), 335 ($\text{TBG} - \text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$), 105 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}^+$) (Found : C, 65.68; H, 4.38; N, 2.99; S, 4.28. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{76}\text{H}_{62}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$: C, 65.75; H, 4.47; N, 3.02; S, 4.61%).

Antimicrobial activities :

All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup plate agar diffusion method by measuring the inhibition zone in mm. The compounds were taken at a concentration of 1 mg/ml using dimethyl sulphoxide as solvent. Amikacin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was used as a standard for antibacterial and fluconazole (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) as a standard for antifungal activity. The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Salmonella typhi* in nutrient agar medium and for antifungal activity against *Candida guilliermondii* and *Microsporum* in potato dextrose agar medium.

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References

- M. Lacova, J. Chovancova, O. Hyblova and S. Varkonda, *Chem. Pap.*, 1990, **44**, 131.
- I. Chnlak, V. Sntorins and V. Sederka, *Chem. Pap.*, 1990, **44**, 131.
- M. Tomoya, N. Shigery, K. Kazuo and S. Testsuo, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **48**, 3763 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **84**, 90463q).
- A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book Practical Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., ELBS, London, 2002.
- I. Widezak, *J. Adv. Carbohydrate Chem.*, 1984, **44**, 91.
- D. Zhiqun, Q. Fangi, Wu Chengtai and Li Wei, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2001, 106.
- H. Krall and R. D. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 629.
- R. M. Silverstein, G. C. Bassler and T. C. Morrill, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 5th ed.,

- John Wiley and Sons, Inc, New York, 1991, pp. 108, 119, 120, 123.
9. N. B. Colthup, L. H. Daly and S. E. Wiberley, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1964, p. 279.
 10. D. H. Williams and I. Fleming, "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., Tata McGraw-Hill Publication, New Delhi, 1988, pp. 40, 41, 47, 53.
 11. Arnold Weissberger, "Physical Methods of Organic Chemistry", Part II, 2nd ed., Interscience Publisher, Inc. New York.